

The Lagrange polynomials for solving a class of fractional variational problems

S. Sabermahani¹

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Y. Ordokhani

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

This paper is devoted to present an efficient approximate method for solving a certain class of fractional variational problems (FVPs). The fractional derivative in these problems is in the Caputo sense. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator for Lagrange polynomials are derived. This operator is utilized to reduce the solution of the problem to a system of algebraic equations. Approximation errors are presented. The examples are included in order to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the suggested method.

Keywords: fractional calculus, Lagrange polynomial, Laplace transform

Mathematics Subject Classification [2010]: 26A33, 44A10

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus with derivatives and integrals of any real or complex order has its origin in the work of Euler, and even earlier in the work of Leibnitz. Shortly after being introduced, the new theory turned out to be very attractive to many famous mathematicians and scientists (e.g. P S Laplace, B Riemann, J Liouville, N H Abel, J B J Fourier et al) due to the numerous possibilities for its applications. Besides mathematics, fractional derivatives and integrals appear in physics, mechanics, engineering, elasticity, dynamics, control theory, electronics, modelling, probability, finance, economics, biology, chemistry, etc [10, 3]. Also, In the large number of scientific and engineering problems, it is necessary to determine the maximal or minimal of a certain functional. Such problems are called variational problems. Most variational problems do not have closed form solutions, so approximation and numerical techniques must be used. Fractional calculus of variations unifies calculus of variations and fractional calculus, by inserting fractional derivatives into variational integrals. This of course occurs naturally in many problems of physics or mechanics, in order to provide more accurate models of physical phenomena. Jumarie [5] is one of the first who has used fractional variational calculus in the analysis of fractional Brownian motion. Some orthogonal polynomials are applied on variational problems to find continuous solutions for these problems, such as Homotopy-perturbation method [1], Chebyshev finite difference method [6], He's variational iteration method [13], Müntz-Legendre polynomials [9], etc.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In the next section, we recall some definitions which are required in this article. Also, we describe the basic properties of Lagrange interpolation. In section 3, we obtain the operator of fractional order integral based on Lagrange polynomials. Section 4 is devoted to the numerical method to solve the fractional variational problems and the approximation errors are presented. In Section 5, we report our numerical findings and demonstrate the high accuracy and effectiveness of the present method by considering numerical examples.

¹speaker

2 Preliminaries and notations

In this section, first we give some basic definitions and properties of fractional calculus theory which are used in this paper and we recall the basic concepts of the Lagrange interpolant for a given function $y(x)$ defined on an interval $[0, 1]$.

Definition 2.1. Riemann-Liouville integral of fractional order $\nu > 0$ is defined as [8]

$$I^\nu f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{\nu-1} f(t) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} x^{\nu-1} * f(x) & \nu > 0, \\ f(x) & \nu = 0, \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

where $x^{\nu-1} * f(x)$ is the convolution product of $x^{\nu-1}$ and $f(x)$. For the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, we have

$$I^\nu x^n = \frac{\Gamma(n+1)}{\Gamma(n+1+\nu)} x^{\nu+n}, \quad n > -1.$$

Lagrange polynomials

Let the set of nodes be given by $x_i \in [0, 1]$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$. Lagrange polynomial based on these points can be defined as follows [11]:

$$L_i(x) := \prod_{j=0, j \neq i}^N \frac{(x-x_j)}{(x_i-x_j)}. \tag{2}$$

Also, Lagrange polynomials satisfy this condition

$$L_i(x_l) = \delta_{il} = \begin{cases} 1, & i = l, \\ 0, & i \neq l \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Theorem 2.2. [12] *If the function $y(x)$ has an $(n+1)$ st derivative, then for every argument x there exists a number ξ in the smallest interval $I[x_0, \dots, x_n, x]$ which contains x and all support x_i , satisfying*

$$E_n(x) = y(x) - y_n(x) = \frac{w(x)y^{(n+1)}(\xi)}{(n+1)!},$$

where $w(x) = (x-x_0)(x-x_1)\dots(x-x_n)$.

Then, we have

$$|E_n(x)| = |y(x) - y_n(x)| = \left| \frac{w(x)y^{(n+1)}(\xi)}{(n+1)!} \right| \leq \frac{M|w(x)|}{(n+1)!}, \tag{4}$$

where $M = \sup_{\xi \in [0,1]} |y^{(n+1)}(\xi)|$.

Remark 2.3. We can rewrite each of $L_i(x)$ as follows [11]

$$L_i(x) = \sum_{s=0}^N \alpha_{is} x^{N-s}, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N. \tag{5}$$

where

$$\alpha_{i0} = \frac{1}{\prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^N (x_i - x_j)} \tag{6}$$

$$\alpha_{is} = \frac{(-1)^s}{\prod_{\substack{j=0 \\ j \neq i}}^N (x_i - x_j)} \sum_{k_s=k_{s-1}+1}^N \cdots \sum_{k_1=0}^{N-s+1} \prod_{r=1}^s x_{k_r}, \tag{7}$$

and $s = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad i \neq k_1 \neq \dots \neq k_s$.

2.1 Function approximation

Suppose that $H = L^2[0, 1]$ is a Hilbert space, $\{L_0(x), L_1(x), \dots, L_N(x)\} \subset H$ is the set of Lagrange polynomials and $Y = span\{L_0(x), L_1(x), \dots, L_N(x)\}$. Let g is an arbitrary element in H . Since Y is a finite dimensional vector space, g has the unique best approximation out of Y such as \tilde{g} , that is

$$\exists \tilde{g} \in Y, \quad s.t \quad \forall y \in Y, \quad \|g - \tilde{g}\| \leq \|g - y\|.$$

Then

$$\forall y \in Y, \quad \langle g - \tilde{g}, y \rangle = 0. \tag{8}$$

where, \langle, \rangle denotes inner product.

On the other hand, since $\tilde{g} \in Y$, there exist unique coefficients c_0, c_1, \dots, c_N such that

$$g(x) \simeq \tilde{g}(x) = \sum_{n=0}^N c_n L_n(x) = C^T L(x), \tag{9}$$

where C and $L(x)$ are $(N + 1) \times 1$ vectors given by:

$$C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_N]^T$$

$$L(x) = [L_0(x), L_1(x), \dots, L_N(x)]^T, \tag{10}$$

and T indicates transposition. Using Eq. (6), we get

$$\langle g(x) - C^T L(x), L_n(x) \rangle = 0, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N,$$

Then the coefficient vector C can be obtained as follows:

$$C^T = G^T D^{-1},$$

where

$$G = [g_0, g_1, \dots, g_N]^T, \quad g_n = \int_0^1 g(x) L_n(x) dx, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N,$$

$$D = \int_0^1 L(x) L^T(x) dx.$$

3 The Reimann-Liouville fraction integral operator of Lagrange polynomials

Using Eq. (1), we obtain the operator I^γ for $L(x)$ in Eq. (10) given by

$$I^\gamma L(x) = \tilde{L}(x, \gamma), \tag{11}$$

where

$$\tilde{L}(x, \gamma) = [I^\gamma L_0(x), I^\gamma L_1(x), \dots, I^\gamma L_N(x)]^T,$$

we use the Laplace transform for Eq. (5) to obtain $I^\gamma L_i(x)$. Then, we have

$$\mathcal{L}(L_i(x)) = \sum_{i=0}^N \alpha_{is} \mathcal{L}(x^{N-s}) = \sum_{i=0}^N \alpha_{is} \frac{\Gamma(N-s+1)}{v^{N-s+1}}.$$

From above equation, we have

$$\mathcal{L}(I^\gamma L_i(x)) = \mathcal{L}\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x^{\gamma-1} * L_i(x)\right) = \frac{1}{v^\gamma} \sum_{i=0}^N \alpha_{is} \frac{\Gamma(N-s+1)}{v^{N-s+1}}. \tag{12}$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform of Eq. (12), we yield $\tilde{L}_i(x, \gamma)$.

$$I^\gamma L_i(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N \alpha_{is} \frac{\Gamma(N-s+1)x^{N-s+\gamma}}{\Gamma(N-s+1+\gamma)}.$$

Notice that the error of this operator is zero.

4 Numerical method

In this paper, we focus on the problems

$$J(y) = \int_0^1 F(x, D^\gamma y(x), D^\nu y(x)) dx \rightarrow \min, \quad n-1 \leq \gamma < n, m-1 \leq \nu < m, m < n \tag{13}$$

with the following conditions:

$$y^{(k)}(0) = y_{0k}, \quad y^{(k)}(1) = y_{1k}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$$

For this problem, we expand $y(x)$ by Lagrange polynomials as:

$$D^\gamma y(x) \simeq C^T L(x), \tag{14}$$

So, we derive

$$y(x) \simeq C^T \tilde{L}(x, \gamma) + E^T L(x), \tag{15}$$

where

$$\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{x^k}{k!} y_{0k} \simeq E^T L(x),$$

and

$$D^\nu y(x) \simeq C^T \tilde{L}(x, \gamma - \nu) + \tilde{E}^T L(x), \tag{16}$$

where

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{x^k}{k!} y_{0k} \simeq \tilde{E}^T L(x),$$

Substituting Eqs (14)-(16) in Eq. (13), then we get

$$J(y) = \int_0^1 F(x, C^T \tilde{L}(x, \gamma) + E^T L(x), C^T \tilde{L}(x, \gamma - \nu) + \tilde{E}^T L(x)) dx \longrightarrow \min, \tag{17}$$

and

$$C^T \tilde{L}(1, \gamma - k) + E^T L(1) = y_{1k}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1,$$

to solve mentioned optimization problem, let

$$J^* = J + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} p_k (C^T \tilde{L}(1, \gamma - k) + E^T L(1) - y_{1k}) \tag{18}$$

where p_k are unknown Lagrange multipliers solved by Newton's iterative method. The necessary conditions for (L, λ_k) to be the extreme of J^* are

$$\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial c_j} = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, n,$$

$$\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial p_k} = 0, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Approximation errors

Now, we derive bounds for the error of the best approximation in terms of Sobolev norms. The Sobolev norm is defined for $\mu \geq 0$ and in the interval (a, b) as follows

$$\|f\|_{H^\mu(a,b)} = \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\mu} \|f^{(k)}(x)\|_{L^2(a,b)}^2 dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Theorem 4.1. *Let $f \in H^\mu(0, 1), \mu \geq 0$. If $\tilde{f} = \sum_{i=0}^N c_i L_i(x)$ is the best approximation of f , then we have*

$$\|f - \tilde{f}\|_{L^2(0,1)} \leq c N^{-\mu} |f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)},$$

and for $1 \leq r \leq \mu$,

$$\|f - \tilde{f}\|_{H^r(0,1)} \leq c N^{2r - \frac{1}{2} - \mu} |f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)},$$

where c depends on μ and $|f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)}$ is defined as follows [4]:

$$|f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)} = \left(\sum_{k=\min\{\mu, N+1\}}^{\mu} \|f^{(k)}\|_{L^2(0,1)}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Proof. Suppose that $f \in H^\mu(0, 1), \mu \geq 0$ and $\sum_{i=0}^N a_i p_i(x)$ is the best approximation of f , where $p_i(x), i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ are the shifted Legendre polynomials. So [4]

$$\|f - \sum_{i=0}^N a_i p_i(x)\|_{L^2(0,1)} \leq cN^{-\mu} |f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)} \tag{19}$$

and for $1 \leq r \leq \mu$,

$$\|f - \sum_{i=0}^N a_i p_i(x)\|_{H^r(0,1)} \leq cN^{2r-\frac{1}{2}-\mu} |f|_{H^{\mu;N}(0,1)} \tag{20}$$

We know that the best approximation is unique [7], then we have

$$\|f - \sum_{i=0}^N a_i p_i(x)\|_{L^2(0,1)} = \|f - \tilde{f}\|_{L^2(0,1)}, \tag{21}$$

and

$$\|f - \sum_{i=0}^N a_i p_i(x)\|_{H^r(0,1)} = \|f - \tilde{f}\|_{H^r(0,1)}, \tag{22}$$

Then, the proof is complete. □

5 Numerical result

In this section, we apply present method to obtain the approximate solution of some examples of the variational problems.

Example 5.1. Consider the following fractional variational problem [6]

$$J[y(x)] = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (D^\gamma y(x))^2 dx, \quad 0 < \gamma \leq 1$$

with the boundary under the following boundary conditions $y(0) = 0, y(1) = 1$. For $\gamma = 1$, the solution of this problem is $y(x) = x$.

We solve this problem by using Lagrange polynomial for $N = 2$ with $x_i = \frac{i}{2}, i = 0, 1, 2$.

$$D^\gamma y(x) \simeq C^T L(x)$$

where $\gamma = 1$ and C is the unknown coefficients vector as follow:

$$C^T = [c_0, c_1, c_2],$$

so we have

$$y(x) = C^T \tilde{L}(x, \gamma).$$

By substituting these approximation in functional and using Newtons iterative method, we obtain

$$C = [1, 1, 1]^T$$

and $y(x) = x$ which is the exact solution of the problem.

Figure 1 shows the curves for exact values of $y(x)$ and numerical values of $y(x)$ for $N = 2$ and $\gamma = 0.95, 0.85, 0.75$.

Figure 1: The behavior of $y(x)$ of Example 1 at $N = 2$ for different values of γ .

Example 5.2. Consider the problem of finding the extremal of the functional [13]

$$J[y] = \int_0^1 (y'^2(x) + y''^2(x))dx,$$

subject to

$$y(0) = 0, \quad y'(0) = 1, \quad y(1) = \sinh(1), \quad y'(1) = \cosh(1).$$

Exact solution for this example is $y(x) = \sinh(x)$. We apply our method with $N = 6$ to solve this problem. In Figure 2, the exact and numerical solutions and also absolute errors are shown.

Figure 2: Comparison of exact and numerical solutions $y(x)$ for $N = 6$ and absolute error in Example 2.

Example 5.3. We consider the following equation [2]

$$J[y] = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (D^\gamma y(x) - f(x))dx,$$

where

$$y(0) = 0, \quad y(1) = 1,$$

and

$$f(x) = \frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta)}{\Gamma(1 + \beta - \gamma)} x^{\beta - \gamma}.$$

In this case, the exact solution of this problem is $y(x) = x^\beta$. We apply present method for solving this equation with $N = 3, \beta = 3$ and different values of γ . Table 1 displays the obtained results.

Table 1: Absolute errors for different values of γ in Example 3.

x	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 0.99$	$\gamma = 0.9$	$\gamma = 0.88$
0.1	1.19416×10^{-16}	5.7474×10^{-6}	5.31203×10^{-5}	6.20514×10^{-5}
0.3	2.22888×10^{-16}	9.26974×10^{-6}	9.99470×10^{-5}	1.21506×10^{-4}
0.5	1.38778×10^{-16}	1.94447×10^{-6}	2.73269×10^{-5}	3.47006×10^{-5}
0.7	8.17568×10^{-17}	7.08276×10^{-6}	6.25435×10^{-5}	2.11732×10^{-5}
0.9	3.19345×10^{-16}	5.37185×10^{-6}	7.23941×10^{-5}	9.19384×10^{-5}

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we present the Riemann-Liouville fraction integral operator of Lagrange polynomials. Then, this operator has been used to approximate numerical solution of fractional variational problems. The error for deriving this operator is zero. Also, the approximation errors are presented. The numerical solution obtained using the proposed technique shows that this method can solve the variational problems effectively.

References

- [1] O. Abdulaziz, I. Hashim, M.S.H. Chowdhury, *Solving variational problems by homotopy perturbation method*. International journal for numerical methods in engineering 75. 6 (2008), pp.709–721.
- [2] O.P. Agrawal, *Generalized EulerLagrange Equations and Transversality Conditions for FVPs in terms of the Caputo Derivative*. Journal of Vibration and Control, 13(9-10), (2007) pp.1217–1237.
- [3] R.L. Bagley, P.J. Torvik, *A theoretical basis for the application of fractional calculus to viscoelasticity*, J. Rheol. 27(3): (1983), pp.201–210.
- [4] C. Canuto, M.Y. Hussaini, A. Quarteroni, T.A. Zang, *Spectral Methods in Fluid Dynamics*, (1988), Springer, New York.
- [5] G. Jumarie, *On the representation of fractional Brownian motion as an integral with respect to (dt) a*. Applied Mathematics Letters, 18(7): (2005) pp.739–748.
- [6] M.M. Khader, A.S. Hendy. *A numerical technique for solving fractional variational problems*. Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences 36. 10 (2013), pp.1281–1289.
- [7] E. Kreyszig, *Introductory Functional Analysis with Applications*, (1978), Wiley, New York.
- [8] S. Mashayekhi, M. Razzaghi. *Numerical solution of distributed order fractional differential equations by hybrid functions*. Journal of Computational Physics, 315 (2016), pp.169–181.
- [9] Y. Ordokhani, P. Rahimkhani, *A numerical technique for solving fractional variational problems by MntzLegendre polynomials*. Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computing, (2017) pp.1–20.
- [10] Y.A. Rossikhin, M.V. Shitikova, *Applications of fractional calculus to dynamic problems of linear and nonlinear hereditary mechanics of solids*, Appl. Mech. Rev. 50 (1997) pp.15–67.

-
- [11] S. Sabermahani, Y. Ordokhani, S. A. Yousefi. *Numerical approach based on fractional-order Lagrange polynomials for solving a class of fractional differential equations*. Computational and Applied Mathematics (2017), pp.1–23.
- [12] J. Stoer, R. Bulirsch, *Introduction to numerical analysis*, Translated by R. Bartels, W. Gautschi, C. Witzgall, Springer-Verlag, 3ed, (1996).
- [13] S.A. Yousefi, M. Dehghan, *The use of He's variational iteration method for solving variational problems*, International Journal of Computer Mathematics, 87 (2010), pp.1299–1314.

Email: `s.saber@alzahra.ac.ir`

Email: `ordokhani@alzahra.ac.ir`